

Educational scenario: Ethical Dilemmas in Religious Studies and Ethnographic Research: an Educational Scenario

For her PhD project, Anna has spent 3 months doing ethnographic research in a community recognizing the Blibluble religion, a controversial minority in her country. She mostly spent time among peaceful common people, but she also made contact with Daniel, a member of a non-violent, but slightly radical wing. Anna approaches the community as a researcher, but as a private person she disagrees with this subcommunity's views. She's been invited to give an interview about her findings in a popular online newspaper.

Issue 1: Daniel told her that core members of the wing are interested in her research and are willing to be interviewed, providing that they will see Anna's own interview before publishing. The subcommunity isn't very communicative, so Anna didn't refuse straight away, but she isn't happy about the condition. Stella, her supervisor, was interested in the option, as she would like to take part in such a research. Stella suggests that communication with the subcommunity may be helpful for society in the long run.

Issue 2: Anna is worried about her publicly accessible newspaper interview and she wonders herself, how far she should talk about the problematic aspects of Blibluble community. The public opinion on Blibluble isn't good and she has seen instances of discrimination, so she wonders how to present the subject as not to worsen the situation. She also feels certain allegiance to the common members she's spent time with. Still, she doesn't want to hide the whole picture from public.

Questions for researchers:

1. In regard to Anna's critical views of the radical wing, consider Anna as a researcher, as an individual person, and also as someone performing an encounter between (sub)cultures. How, in your opinion, should she balance her feelings and a) her scientific distance, and b) her respect for other (sub)cultures' views and lifestyle?
2. Is Anna's feeling of allegiance an unacceptable bias? Do you think it is possible to actually keep scientific distance in this kind of research, spending a long time living among respondents?
3. Consider Anna's dilemmas between objectivity and social impact, which are both matters of scientific integrity. How would you (do you) work with negative public opinion on your respondents? What do you think about Stella's suggestion that potential help for the long term communication with the group may be worth the one time breach of integrity?

Questions for supervisors:

1. Do you think Stella's own interest in the issue is problematic, when she gives advice to Anna about her dilemma?
2. If you were Stella, how would you ensure that Anna knew she could decide either way without consequences on your relationship?